

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF QUALITY AND EFFICIENCY ASSESSMENT IN THE SERVICE SECTOR

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Abstract. In this article, the theoretical aspects of the quality and efficiency evaluation criteria in the service sector are revealed by the author. In addition, proposals and recommendations have been developed on the specific characteristics of these theoretical aspects.

Key words: service, quality, efficiency, theoretical foundations.

Education, qualifications and work experience of an employee are not as important for the head of the organization as a specific result. Therefore, the main criterion for evaluating the effectiveness of work is the effectiveness of the work of personnel. The remaining indicators - personal data, qualifications, experience - are taken into account as an auxiliary, and not a primary criterion.

Performance evaluation: concept and meaning

The personnel manager, immediate supervisor or employer has the right to assess the effectiveness of the performance of duties by the organization's personnel. An analysis of the productivity of the professional activity of an individual employee, an assessment of the fulfillment of his tasks, allow us to note the effectiveness of the functioning of the entire company.

When evaluating the effectiveness of the work of personnel, the following are taken into account:

- amount of work performed;
- complexity of the assigned tasks;
- features of assigned functional duties;
- results of work.

A person can cope with his duties, but never invest in deadlines, constantly distract colleagues to help with work, while efficiency is the sum of two indicators:

- Time spent on achieving the result.
- Expended resources.

An experienced HR specialist is well aware that it will be possible to increase the efficiency of personnel activities if three conditions are met. And all three conditions are aimed at the interaction of the leader and the subordinate:

1. The desire to work must become mutual. To get a "return" from an ordinary employee, the boss should talk about "bonuses" in the form of a bonus or career growth. Thus, both parties benefit: the employee improves his financial situation or acquires a new status, and the organization increases profits due to the efficiency of the use of personnel.

2. Using the "personal" / "selfish" needs of the subordinate to increase his performance. Everyone has their own interest. If you manage to find out what is important for a person, this can be used as motivation.

3. The interest of management in the team of workers. If subordinates feel their "need", they understand that the company is interested in each of them, they try not to disappoint the management, and the results of work will serve as a reward for both the subordinate and the manager.

How did the idea of performance appraisal come about? Every employer wants to know what they are spending their money on. It is important for him to understand that the benefits of the employee's activities correspond to the funds invested in him. Performance evaluation is carried out to find out:

- the level of work of the management system, as well as the organization of the distribution of functional responsibilities among the staff;
- whether an individual employee copes with the tasks assigned to him, and to what extent;
- "Necessity" of the employee for the company: the ratio of the company's expenses for the maintenance of the employee with his personal contribution to the profit of the enterprise;
- compliance of the amount of work performed with the income received;
- what methods of motivation will be effective for the staff;
- how promising the employee is, and whether it is worth investing in his training to increase the efficiency and productivity of his work, based on the interests of the organization.

The introduction of KPI (key performance indicators) assessment of personnel is a popular technique for modern managers.

In practice, it looks like this: the boss sets certain goals and objectives for the staff. Some employees get the job done, others don't. According to the assessment and reward: those who completed the plan - a bonus (cash reward), the rest - thanks for the work (or trying to cope with it). The purpose of such assessments is fair wages.

The employer is primarily interested in evaluating the effectiveness. Based on the performance indicators, he appoints the payment for the staff. For example, a sales manager can be interested in the percentage of deals made. The higher his personal efficiency, the higher the average monthly income. Salaries are important for office workers. And the amount of salary will depend on the assessment of the effectiveness of their work. But with the creative staff - designers or programmers - everything is much more complicated. Russian companies are just beginning to use the KPI indicator in assessing the productivity of creative work. The remuneration of employees of companies is based on the subjective assessment of the manager or employer. Only a part of the leaders confess their method of evaluation, while the rest assiduously hide it.

Not all managers manage to successfully implement a performance appraisal system for their subordinates. And the reason lies both in the unsuccessful method and in the lack of efficiency of the leader himself. What problems of performance analysis can arise and why?

The first barrier to the successful implementation of a system for assessing the level of performance of staff performance of their duties is the resistance of the team. Why is this happening? There are a number of reasons:

- **concerns about innovation.** The staff is afraid of change, believing that the volume of work will increase, and the size of the salary will decrease;
- **complex scheme.** A multi-level system for evaluating the effectiveness of the use of personnel confuses and demotivates the employee. If an employee cannot understand what he did wrong and why he was paid less, this negatively affects his performance and attitude to work;
- **incomprehensible wage system.** If the bonus is paid based on the results of work for the past or even the month before last, the employee is disoriented: he worked worse, but earned more;
- **the difference in the assessment of completed tasks and the overall effectiveness of the employee and his manager.** And such estimates rarely coincide;
- **Achievement of the set goal does not always depend entirely on the activity of the employee.** What he considers correct, aesthetic, may not please the customer at all. And the work will have to be redone, making edits again and again. Therefore, evaluating the activities of "creative" workers, the manager should apply a special method or an individual approach;
- **the need to spend time on reports.** Who will like to write a detailed report after completing the work, indicating the time spent, meeting deadlines and analyzing their own mistakes.

The assessment of the professional level of the personnel is set on the basis of the analysis:

- the amount of theoretical knowledge of the employees of the organization;
- the ability of staff to apply knowledge in practice.

Methods for evaluating a particular employee allow the manager to determine the ability of a subordinate to create a "product" that is necessary for the organization, at the lowest cost to the latter.

The most popular methods of personnel assessment are:

Regular interviews with existing employees help identify problems among staff, avoid or resolve conflicts that arise among colleagues during work, and identify potential leaders and outsiders. Of course, the disadvantage of such assessments is their subjectivity. After all, interviews are often conducted by one specialist.

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